

Exploring occupant detection model generalizability for residential buildings using supervised learning with IEQ sensors

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ABSTRACT

This study explores two modeling approaches for occupancy detection at room level for residential buildings in Denmark. The aim is to assess the performance and generalizability of occupant detection models using XGBoost method trained on a rich dataset comprising indoor environmental quality (IEQ) variables and occupancy ground truth. A global approach (all rooms) and a room-specific approach are considered. After a thorough feature-selection and importance analysis process, the occupancy detection models (ODMs) are trained and tested in a nested cross-validation schema. The time of the day, indoor CO₂ concentration, and feature transforms related to short-term IEQ dynamics were found to be the most important features of the ODMs. Both the global and room-specific models show good occupancy prediction performance, especially for bedrooms. When tested for generalizability with an unseen dataset from a different residential building, the ODMs maintain very good performance for the bedroom but not for the office room. This discrepancy could be explained by significant differences in occupancy and ventilation patterns, and large air infiltration from adjacent rooms. Although currently limited in terms of generalizability, XGBoost-based ODMs using IEQ data have the potential to provide robust and scalable occupancy detection for occupant-centric control and occupant-aware building performance assessments. The IEQ dataset with occupancy ground truth collected for this study is made available in open access.

1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation

Occupant detection has gained significant attention due to its broad applicability and benefits for the optimized control of buildings [1]. The ability to accurately identify and monitor occupancy levels within public, commercial, office, and residential buildings holds great promise for enhancing energy efficiency, improving indoor environmental quality (IEQ), increasing users' satisfaction, and enabling personalized comfort systems [2]. Indeed, detecting occupancy can be the foundation for optimized activation of lighting, electrical appliances, heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems: Occupant-centric control (OCC) or occupant-aware control [3,4]. Conversely, it can allow deviation from IEQ requirements when there is no occupancy [5]. Research has shown that OCC can save up to 47 % of energy use for HVAC systems [6] and 79 % for artificial lighting [7].

Residential buildings account for a significant share of the global energy demand [8]. They are generally considered the least energy-efficient part of the building stock. They thus hold considerable potential for implementing energy-efficient initiatives such as for

example OCC leveraging occupant detection models. However, residential buildings present different challenges than commercial spaces (e.g., office buildings) as occupancy patterns can be more diverse and unpredictable [9]. Unlike commercial spaces, where occupants are primarily present within regular or set working/opening hours, residential occupancy is not strictly confined to a fixed schedule. It can vary greatly depending on the occupants' lifestyle, age, work, cultural background, and personal preferences [10]. Moreover, privacy concerns are more important in residential settings. There's a higher risk of a perceived violation of privacy in a personal space, making occupants more cautious and potentially resistant to data collection. Thus, collecting occupancy ground truth and IEQ data in dwellings can be a hurdle.

1.2. Background on occupant detection modeling

Within the last decade, several reviews on occupant detection were published. Rueda et al. [11] categorized published literature using analytical, data-driven, and knowledge-based methods. Data-driven methods were found to be used in 75 % of the explored articles, with Support Vector Machine, Hidden-Markov Model, and k-Nearest Neighbors being the most commonly applied algorithms. Residential buildings were only present in approximately 25 % of the studies. Saha et al. [12]

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations Definition

AUROC	Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve
BIM	Building Information Modeling
CAV	Constant Air Flow
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DT	Decision Tree
GBDTs	Gradient Boosted Decision Trees
GVIF	Generalized Variance Inflation Factor
HMM	Hidden Markov Model
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IEQ	Indoor Environment Quality
KNN	k-Nearest Neighbors
MCC	Matthew's Correlation Coefficient

MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
OCC	Occupant-Centric Control
ODM	Occupancy Detection Model
RF	Random Forest
SATO	Self-Assessment Towards Optimization of Building Energy
SVM	Support Vector Machine
VIF	Variance Inflation Factor
XGBoost	eXtreme Gradient Boosting

Room type abbreviations and definitions

B	Bedroom
KL	Kitchen/Living Room
K	Kitchen
L	Living room
O	Office

also analyzed algorithms found in the literature: Tree classifications (e. g., Random Forest), Support Vector Machine, neural networks, and clustering methods were found to be the most applied algorithms. Deep and transfer learning were explored by Sayed et al. [13]. In that review, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) were the most applied algorithms. 10 % of the studies addressed residential buildings. Trivedi et al. [14] investigated sensor types, sensing approaches, and typical applications in occupancy detection. The fusion of two or more occupancy sensing approaches was found to provide more accurate and reliable results. Chen et al. [15] also studied which sensing methods were the most used. PIR (Passive InfraRed) sensors, smart energy meters, IEQ sensors, cameras, Wi-Fi routers were among the most common data sources for occupancy estimation. Sensor fusion was also found to be the most applied and robust approach for occupant detection modeling. Mulia et al. [16] indicated that CO₂ concentration and PIR sensor signal were the most popular features. However, no specific trend in the use of performance metrics or model types could be found. Jin et al. [17] reviewed studies on occupancy forecasting. Office buildings were found to be the most investigated type for operation optimization of HVAC systems. Enhancing data transparency, generalizability and robustness were identified as future challenges to overcome, as this is sparsely documented in the published literature.

Now focusing on occupancy detection in residential buildings, a literature search has been conducted on the Scopus database [18] and Google Scholar with the following keywords: *Residential buildings, occupant detection, occupant estimation, occupancy forecasting* (and with variants of "occupant"). 19 articles were found to focus on residential buildings for occupant detection, occupancy estimation or forecasting. Some common occupancy detection methods used in commercial buildings, such as video surveillance or access control systems, may not be acceptable or feasible in a residential context. The body of datasets with occupancy in dwellings is very limited. One group published a rich dataset with occupancy ground truth, IEQ data, audio and video data for six single-family houses during one month [19]. Other alternative methods using smart home devices [20–25], electricity data [20,26–31], or IEQ sensors [23,32–38] are considered less invasive for estimating occupancy in dwellings. However, utilization of electricity data is often at household level and requires high-temporal resolution data to catch the dynamics of occupant's interactions with the equipment and differentiate that from the baseload [28]. IEQ measurements in a room can be influenced by the proximity to other occupied rooms and air infiltration through open doors or windows, potentially making IEQ sensor-based occupancy detection models (ODMs) unreliable. On the contrary, occupancy in smaller rooms with lower or constant ventilation rates has been found easier to estimate [32].

A significant portion of the existing literature focuses on developing

models tailored to specific datasets and building cases, which can cause certain challenges. These models often excel in the conditions they were trained under but may fail when faced with unseen data from buildings and occupants with very different characteristics. Given the diverse settings and conditions under which occupant detection systems might be deployed, ODMs must demonstrate robustness and adaptability. In essence, there is a demand for generalizable models that can predict occupant presence even when encountering data that are not generated by the room or building used for training and testing. Secondly, the performance assessment of an occupant detection model accuracy is not standardized. The literature presents a mix of both qualitative and quantitative performance assessments, but the use of metrics accounting for imbalanced classes is very rare. Lastly, the literature is typically lacking information on the training and testing data splits and the hyperparameters used for the model's development. This compromises transparency and decreases reproducibility and comparison across studies.

1.3. Novelty and contribution of the current study

This study aims to develop and test a generalizable occupancy detection (binary classification: Occupied or unoccupied) method using IEQ sensors (indoor temperature, relative humidity, and CO₂ concentration) from a multi-story residential building and test the developed model with unseen data from a single-family house with comparable characteristics. These IEQ sensors are well accepted in dwellings, partly privacy-preserving, and are expected to be commonly installed in future smart homes. In the context of machine learning, the generalizability of a model is interpreted here as the ability of the latter to perform well on new, unseen data originating from a building case that is not correlated to that of the training data. In other words, what is the model's capability to generalize its learnings from one set of data (training data) to new and different data (application target data) [39].

The main aim of the present work is to develop a robust ODM that can be applied in various real-world scenarios. The research questions associated with that aim are as follows.

- Are there significant differences between the performance of a room-specific (trained for a specific room type) and a global (trained for all types of room) ODM?
- To what extent can the trained ODMs correctly predict occupancy from unseen data collected in residential buildings with similar characteristics?
- What factors influence the model's generalization?

This study offers several novel contributions to the field of occupancy

detection in residential buildings. A unique aspect lies in the investigation of a multi-story apartment building, encompassing five apartments situated in a Nordic climate. Furthermore, a rich and detailed-described curated dataset is made available in open access. It contains IEQ features and occupancy ground truth at room level for all five apartments with a 15-min. temporal resolution over seven days. Additional metadata and detailed case study information were also collected. Such datasets are very rare and clearly lacking in the development of machine learning applications for ODM in residential buildings.

The modeling approach employed in the present work is the eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) decision tree method [40,41]. XGBoost models can present very high performance for classification problems. However, only two articles report the use of XGBoost model for ODM [29,32], and only one of them uses IEQ data [32].

Finally, the model development process includes a feature importance analysis and selection, hyperparameter optimization, model performance assessment with nested-cross validations, further testing on unseen data, and discussions on model generalizability. Currently, no such work has been done with XGBoost decision tree models for occupancy detection applications using IEQ data of residential buildings. The authors of this article hope that this thorough methodology will help and inspire researchers to improve machine learning practices in the built environment and enhance the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) [42] for collected data with valuable ground truth and publishing data treatment code.

After introducing the dataset for the model training (Section 2) and the dataset for the model application (Section 3), the detailed ODM development workflow is presented (Section 4). Furthermore, the results from the model development, evaluation, and application with unseen data are presented and discussed in Section 5. The article closes with conclusions and suggestions for future investigations (Section 6).

2. Dataset for model development

2.1. Case study building and occupants

The case study building used to develop, train, and test the ODM is a multi-story residential apartment block built in 1949/50 and renovated in 2012/2013 to a low-energy class A+ (according to Danish regulation in 2023). It is located in an urban area situated in the Northern part of Denmark. The building is semi-sheltered and neighbored primarily by other residential buildings of comparable or lesser height [43]. The building has five staircases consisting of either three or six apartments, for a total of 24 apartments in the block. This study focuses on five apartments in one staircase. One can see the layouts of two adjacent flats in Fig. 1.

This study encompasses five apartments (16 rooms in total) distributed over three floors. Three apartments are of the “left type” (living room, office, bedroom, kitchen, bathroom) with a floor area of 72 m², and two are of the “right type” (living room/kitchen, bedroom, bathroom) with a floor area of 55 m² [43]. All apartments have balanced mechanical ventilation operating with constant air volume (CAV) flow. For the apartments to the left, the inlet fresh air supply is located in the offices and bedrooms, and the exhaust is located in the kitchens and bathrooms. For the apartments to the right, the inlet fresh air supply is located in the bedrooms and living rooms/kitchens, and the exhaust is located in the bathrooms and in the living rooms/kitchens. The supply and exhaust air flow is around 15–20 m³/h (directly measured on site in each apartment).

Six occupants were recruited in the five different apartments to be part of the monitoring campaign. The recruited occupant’s apartment, animals, gender, occupation, and associated room numbers can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1
Main characteristics of the studied apartment and occupants.

Apartment	Number of occupants	Genders	Animals	Occupation	Room numbers and room type in parenthesis
Apartment 1 (55 m ²)	1	Male	None	Retired	1 (bedroom) and 2 (living room/kitchen)
Apartment 2 (72 m ²)	1	Female	None	Retired	3 (bedroom), 4 (kitchen), 5 (living room) and 6 (office)
Apartment 3 (55 m ²)	1	Male	None	Retired	7 (bedroom) and 8 (living room/kitchen)
Apartment 4 (72 m ²)	1	Female	Indoor cat	Librarian	9 (bedroom), 10 (kitchen), 11 (living room) and 12 (office)
Apartment 5 (72 m ²)	2	Female and male	None	Nurse and shipping manager	13 (bedroom), 14 (kitchen), 15 (living room) and 16 (office)

Fig. 1. Floor plan of the two types of apartments in the studied residential building case [43].

2.2. Collection and curation of the indoor environment data and occupancy ground truth

A number of data features and building characteristics are recorded and collected together with the occupancy ground truth in each room of each apartment under study. Those recorded information and monitoring variables include the date, day of the week, time of the day, room type, apartment number, indoor operative temperature, indoor CO₂ concentration, and indoor relative humidity. These monitoring variables are commonly measured by modern building management systems (BMS) in commercial, public and office buildings. It is believed that those variables will also become more and more systematically monitored in future smart buildings and dwellings equipped with smart home automation systems as they are fundamental to assessing indoor environmental quality (thermal comfort and indoor air quality) and controlling HVAC systems accordingly.

The aforementioned IEQ variables are measured with standalone battery-powered wireless devices. The logging rate is set to 5 min. The recorded data is then down-sampled at a 15-min logging rate to match the temporal resolution of the occupancy ground truth. The measurement data is regularly transferred onto a secured server and later retrieved via a REST API. All sensors were calibrated in a laboratory prior to their installation in the building (except for the bathrooms).

In order to provide some information about the short-term dynamics of the indoor environment and possibly enhance the occupancy predictors, additional data features are generated as transforms of the time series of recorded indoor CO₂ concentration, indoor operative temperature and indoor relative humidity. For these three IEQ variables and for each recording time step, the corresponding new features are the *difference between the current value and the average of the past hour*, the *difference between the current value and the previously recorded value* (15 min prior), and the *mean average of the latest four recordings* (mean average over the last hour). All measured data and feature transforms are considered inputs for the development of the occupancy models. However, only the most significant ones are selected during the feature importance analysis and selection (see Model Development section).

In the global model, the room type is a one-hot-encoded time-independent input [44]. In both global and room-specific models, the *day of the week* and *hour of the day* features are cyclic encoded to a cos-sine transformation [45,46]. The final dataset consists of vertical concatenation of the 16 datasets corresponding to each room (numbers 1–16).

“Ground truth” is commonly defined as the most certain or accurate value that one can obtain for a given observation [47]. In the current study, occupancy ground truth (how many occupants are present in a room at a given time) is directly determined from occupants’ feedback via an activity logbook that the recruited occupants filled out over seven days, from January 30, 2023 to February 06, 2023, with a 15-min temporal resolution. The logbook consists of one logging paper sheet to be filled in per day and arranged in each room (except the bathroom). The data collection campaign took place during the winter time. The occupants did not open their windows during that period. The original logbooks can be downloaded from a dedicated GitHub repository [48]. Further description of the measurement equipment, collection of indoor environmental data, and occupancy ground truth can be found in a dedicated technical report [49].

2.3. Overview of the collected dataset

The monitoring campaign in this building case thus only covers seven full days with occupancy ground truth. This dataset could be qualified as small in the machine learning community. However, one should keep in mind the difficulty in collecting such ground truth and data in residential buildings. If surveys and logbooks are a relatively well-accepted and reliable solution to collect occupancy ground truth and activity information in a non-intrusive and privacy-preserving manner, it is very challenging to incentivize participants to be part of

such a campaign for more than a few days. Seven complete days of high-quality room-level 15-min. resolution data in open access for six occupants in 16 rooms and five apartments is currently non-existent in the scientific literature. The present dataset, although modest in size, is thus a fair compromise between the temporal and special resolution, occupancy ground truth accuracy, participants’ motivation, and available resources. The analysis of this dataset reveals distinct patterns in most of the rooms during the monitoring campaign, indicating suitability for ODM applications in similar setups and seasons.

2.3.1. IEQ data

The collected and curated IEQ dataset comprises 673 recordings of indoor CO₂ concentration, operative temperature, and relative humidity in each of the 16 different rooms over the five studied apartments, which constitutes a total of 10 768 data lines (15-min. logging interval over seven days). One can see an overview of the collected IEQ data for the different rooms in the box plot and whiskers in Fig. 2, Fig. 3, and Fig. 4 (interquartile range (IQR) of 25 %, median, 75 %, whiskers calculated as $\pm 1.5 * IQR$, diamond-shaped markers as outliers outside the $1.5 * IQR$ range). On the X-axis, each room is identified by its apartment number (Apt. X), room number (RX), and room type (B: Bedroom, K/L: Kitchen/Living room, K: Kitchen, L: Living room, O: Office).

Naturally, the indoor CO₂ concentration is generally higher during the presence than the absence of occupants since human’s exhale CO₂ and are the main source of the latter in residential buildings. One can also observe in Fig. 2 that there are some high CO₂ concentration outliers in the unoccupied categories, especially for bedrooms. This is due to the fact that when occupants leave a room, the CO₂ concentration does not drop immediately, but decays progressively (exponential decay).

The differences in the indoor operative temperatures between presence and absence are limited. The variability is more important between the different rooms. The presence of occupants does not seem to significantly alter the room temperature, although the latter is usually slightly higher during occupancy. This is expected in a low-energy building during winter with low use of natural ventilation (in here, no window opening at all) and an assumed well-functioning heating system (no complaints from occupants or alarms in the BMS). The difference in indoor temperature between the rooms is thus explained by different temperature setpoints selected by the occupants. Similarly, the indoor relative humidity is not significantly influenced by occupancy but is generally slightly higher when humans are present in a room.

The IEQ overview per room type is presented in the box plots and whiskers of Fig. 5, Fig. 6, and Fig. 7. As one can observe in Fig. 5, the bedrooms have the highest CO₂ concentrations, because of longer occupancy periods and minimal ventilation. A similar trend is visible in offices, while the kitchens and living rooms have minor differences between occupancy and vacancy. This might be due to larger indoor volume and air mixing with adjacent rooms. As previously mentioned, one can observe from Figs. 6 and 7 that the indoor operative temperature and relative humidity tend to be slightly higher in all room types when occupied.

2.3.2. Occupancy ground truth

The reported occupancy (via logbooks) was slightly adjusted to form the occupancy ground truth. It was ensured that in each apartment where only one occupant lives, the latter could only be in one room at a time. There were only 2–10 minor adjustments in each flat, representing around 1.5% of the reported occupancy. For the apartment with two occupants, recorded occupancy in two different rooms at the same time was kept.

To perform machine learning for classification applications, it is important to assess the imbalance ratio of the used datasets. The imbalance ratio is essential for choosing the optimal hyperparameters (avoid overfitting towards the majority class), performance metrics, and modeling techniques. In the present case, the imbalance ratio for the occupancy ground truth is calculated as the ratio of the number of

Fig. 2. Indoor CO₂ concentration distribution in the different studied rooms, categorized as occupied or unoccupied.

Fig. 3. Indoor operative temperature distribution in the different studied rooms, categorized as occupied or unoccupied.

samples in the majority class (unoccupied) to the number of samples in the minority class (occupied):

$$\text{Imbalance Ratio} = \frac{\text{Number of samples in Class 0}}{\text{Number of samples in Class 1}}$$

Table 2 and Table 3 present the imbalance ratio for each studied room and each room type, respectively. The average dataset imbalance for the minority and majority classes is approximately [1:3], indicating that for each minority class point (occupied), there are three majority class points (unoccupied). As one can observe in Tables 2 and 3, the imbalance ratio varies highly between the rooms, which reflects the differences in the percentage of presence time in the respective rooms.

One can observe in Fig. 8 the length distribution of the occupancy periods in all studied rooms during the measurement campaign. Most of the occupancy periods last less than 1 hour, corresponding to occupants regularly moving from one room to another within an apartment. There

is also a small peak in occupancy length ranging from 6 hours to 10 hours, corresponding to occupants sleeping in their bedrooms.

A detailed overview of the dataset with time series and scatter plots of the different monitored variables in the different rooms of each flat can be found in a dedicated technical report [49].

3. Dataset for model application and generalizability assessment

The ODM trained on the abovementioned dataset can be applied and further tested on a new dataset (unseen by the model during training) from a different building case, provided that this dataset has the right features, metadata, and occupancy ground truth (for performance assessment). The performance assessment of the ODM with this new unseen dataset can inform on the generalizability of the ODM.

Fig. 4. Indoor relative humidity distribution in the different studied rooms, categorized as occupied or unoccupied.

Fig. 5. Indoor CO₂ concentration distribution in the different room types, categorized as occupied or unoccupied.

3.1. Dataset criteria for suitability of the developed model

To use the developed ODM on a new dataset, the latter must meet the following criteria.

- **Time series data must comprise the following features:** Indoor CO₂ concentration, indoor operative temperature, indoor relative humidity, date and time stamp.
- **Metadata:** The time series data must correspond to one of the following room types: kitchen, living room, bedroom, office or combined living room and kitchen.
- **Building characteristics:** Residential building with low ventilation/infiltration, minimum air infiltration between rooms, typical room size, and common occupancy schedule.

- **Season:** The developed ODM is only valid for the cold winter period (assuming no window opening).

3.2. Selected application dataset

One dataset [32] was found to have the necessary characteristics defined above for the application and further testing of the developed ODM. For further testing, ground truth is necessary. The found dataset originates from the SmartVENT project [50]. Only two out of three rooms in this Danish single-family house case were found to be suitable for ODM application according to the aforementioned criteria: The bedroom and the small office. The imbalance ratio of the bedroom dataset is [1:1.4], and [1:6.4] for the office dataset. The percentage of presence in the bedroom is 40 %, and 13 % in the small office.

Fig. 6. Indoor relative humidity distribution in the different room types, categorized as occupied or unoccupied.

Fig. 7. Room temperature distribution in the different room types, categorized as occupied or unoccupied.

One can observe in the box plots and whiskers of Fig. 9 that the trends for indoor CO₂ concentration, operative temperature, and relative humidity are similar to those emphasized in the ODM development and training dataset (see previous section). The CO₂ concentration is larger during occupancy, especially in the bedroom, while the operative temperature and relative humidity are only slightly higher during occupied periods.

To apply the ODM to this new dataset, the latter has to be prepared as follows: Feature transforms related to IEQ variable dynamics are computed, the date and time features are transformed using a cyclic encoding [45,46], and the room type is one-hot encoded [44].

4. Model development

4.1. Selected algorithm

The occupant detection algorithm used in this study was chosen based on 1) being suitable for supervised binary classification problems, 2) applicability on imbalanced datasets, 3) clear documentation and 4) an initial benchmarking of commonly used classification models: Support Vector Machine, Logistic Regression, Random Forest, k-Nearest Neighbor, Naive Bayes and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost). The benchmarking results can be found in a dedicated technical report [51]. For the present study, the XGBoost model was one of the top performers. XGBoost is a decision tree-based classifier generated with the XGBoost methodology [40,41]. It is known for showing good performance, can

Table 2
Imbalance ratios and calculated presence percentage for each room.

Apartment number	Room number	Room type	~ Imbalance ratio [occupied:unoccupied]	Percentage of presence time in the dataset [%]
1	1	Bedroom	[1:3]	27
	2	Kitchen/living room	[1:0.60]	63
	Total	-	[1:2]	80
2	3	Bedroom	[1:2]	35
	4	Kitchen	[1:2]	32
	5	Living room	[1:5]	18
	6	Office	[1:44]	2
	Total	-	[1:13]	86
	7	Bedroom	[1:2]	32
3	8	Kitchen/living room	[1:0.90]	52
	Total	-	[1:1]	84
	9	Bedroom	[1:2]	35
4	10	Kitchen	[1:18]	5
	11	Living room	[1:7]	13
	12	Office	[1:44]	2
	Total	-	[1:18]	54
	13	Bedroom	[1:1]	45
5	14	Kitchen	[1:9]	10
	15	Living room	[1:2]	33
	16	Office	[1:9]	10
	Total	-	[1:5]	98^a
Average all apartments	-	[1:3]	-	

^a Two occupants can be in two different rooms at the same time.

Table 3
Imbalance ratios and calculated presence percentage for each room type.

Room type	~ Imbalance ratio of dataset [presence: absence]	Total number of data points	Average percentage presence time in the dataset [%]
Bedroom	[1:2]	3.365	34
Kitchen/living room	[1:0.7]	1.345	57
Kitchen	[1:5]	2.018	16
Living room	[1:4]	2.018	21
Office	[1:20]	2.018	7

handle imbalanced datasets and has a wide range of hyperparameters for customization. However, this approach can be computationally demanding because of longer hyperparameter tuning and is less interpretable than simpler decision tree-based models. The XGBoost model used in this work is developed with the scikit-learn Python library [52].

4.2. Model types

Six ODMs were developed: Five room-specific models, one for each of the five room types (trained and tested with only data from bedroom, living room, kitchen, living room/kitchen, and office, respectively), and one global model, trained and tested with data from all room types, and thus suitable to detect occupancy in all rooms.

Fig. 8. Length distribution of the occupancy periods in all studied rooms during the measurement campaign. Each bar in the histogram represents 15 min of additional occupancy length.

Fig. 9. Indoor CO₂ concentration, relative humidity, and operative temperature distribution in each room of the new application dataset, categorized as occupied or unoccupied.

Pros global model

- Deploying and maintaining one model rather than multiple models can be easier.
- Offers a uniform approach to predictions, which can make it simpler to troubleshoot and refine.
- When model improvements are made, they benefit all categories simultaneously.
- May be more robust and scalable for applications on buildings not present in the training datasets.

Cons global model

- May miss out on patterns that are specific to individual room types.
- If one category is overrepresented in the data, the model may be biased towards it.
- A single error in the model can affect predictions across all categories.

Pros room-specific model

- Tailored to the unique characteristics of each category.
- It can evolve or be updated separately based on the specific needs of each category.
- A specific set of features can be selected for each model, which might be better suited for a specific room type.
- A problem or error in one model does not affect the others.

Cons room-specific model

- Multiple models can be more complex to manage, deploy, and update.
- Each model might have access to less data for training and testing.
- Some models might perform better than others, leading to inconsistency in overall predictions.

4.3. Machine learning workflow

Fig. 10 gives an overview of the whole machine learning workflow (pipeline) used in this study. After collecting and curating the data from the building study case, a feature importance analysis is conducted to assess which input variables should be included in the ODMs. After selecting the appropriate features for the different ODMs, nested cross-validation with a hyperparameter optimization (grid search) is performed to assess the average performance of the trained models with different training/testing/evaluation splits. Final models are then trained with all collected data and a hyperparameter optimization. Finally, these ODMs are applied to a new unseen dataset originating from another building case to assess the generalizability and applicability of the former.

4.4. Selected performance metrics

Several steps of the machine learning process described above necessitate the use of performance metrics to assess capability to detect occupancy from IEQ data. Nine quantitative performance metrics that

Fig. 10. The machine learning pipeline of the whole occupant detection modeling process.

are commonly used for machine learning classification problem [53,54] are here chosen to evaluate the ODMs: *Accuracy*, *balanced accuracy*, *confusion matrix*, *precision*, *recall*, *F1-score*, *Matthew's correlation coefficient* (MCC), *Brier score*, and *Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve* (AUROC). Each metric provides different insights into the model performance. Together they provide a holistic assessment of the ODMs' performance. *Accuracy* only accounts for the total number of correct predictions over the total number of predictions [55], which can be misleading for imbalanced datasets. The *confusion matrix* [56] presents the number of true negatives (number of cases correctly predicted as negative), true positives (number of cases correctly predicted as positive), false positives (number of negative cases incorrectly predicted as positive), and false negatives (number of positive cases incorrectly predicted as negative). *Balanced accuracy* [57,58] is especially suited for imbalanced datasets, for which the performance can be biased towards the majority class (overfitting). Contrary to *accuracy*, it accounts for the differences in the sizes of the classes in a dataset. *Precision* and *recall* calculate the ability of the model to correctly label true positives and true negatives, respectively [59,60]. The *F1-score* is the average of the *precision* and the *recall* [61]. However, for a strongly imbalanced dataset, the *F1-score* can be irrelevant and should be completed by other metrics, such as MCC. The latter specifically accounts for true negatives and false

positives [62,63]. The AUROC provides insight into how well the classes are distinguished by the model [64,65]. Lastly, the *Brier-score loss* measures the mean squared difference between the predicted probability and the actual outcome [66]. The performance metrics are all calculated using the Scikit-learn Python library [52]. More details on the performance metrics can be found in a dedicated technical report [51].

4.5. Feature selection and importance analysis

The model feature selection process is shown in Fig. 11. After dataset preparation, the feature selection is performed with 4095 feature combinations for each model type (global and room-specific). However, training XGBoost models with hyperparameter optimization for so many runs would be extremely computationally costly, and training XGBoost models without hyperparameter optimization would provide unreliable results. Random Forest (RF) is considered insensitive to hyperparameter optimization and is generally robust to overfitting [67]. It is reasonable to assume that the results from feature selection and importance analysis [68,69] are the similar for RF and XGBoost (two decision tree-based algorithms). RF is thus used in a 10-fold stratified group k-fold cross validation for the feature selection and importance analysis as it significantly decreases the computation burden.

Fig. 11. Model feature selection process.

The best-performing model from all feature combinations is selected based on all nine performance metrics (with a special emphasis on *balanced accuracy* and MCC) and expert knowledge, specifically aiming at minimizing the number of redundant features (risks of multicollinearity [70]). This was crucial to ensure a balance between the number of features and their actual impact on the model's performance.

The selected model is then tested for multicollinearity by calculating the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for the room-specific models' features [71] and Generalized Variance Inflation Factor (GVIF) for the global model's features [72]. If the selected model's features have all a VIF or GVIF below 5, these features are considered optimal and will be used for the next step: Nested cross-validation with the XGBoost model. If the VIF or GVIF is not adequate, the model's features are discarded, and a new top-performing model from the feature combination is tested.

The feature importance of the final model is then computed. The importance of a feature (Gini impurity) is based on its contribution in a single decision tree within an RF model. Importance scores are then normalized so that they sum up to 1, which eases comparing the relative contribution of each feature [68,73,74].

4.6. Nested cross-validation

To get an unbiased and robust performance estimate, a nested cross-validation approach is used to evaluate the XGBoost ODM with the selected optimum features [75,76]. It consists of.

- 1) Model evaluation with a 10-fold outer loop (group shuffle split [77]) on 20 % of the dataset.
- 2) Model selection with a 10-fold inner loop (stratified group k-fold split [78]) on 80 % of the dataset.

Each stratified fold is formed according to the day of the year and room number, meaning that the data from one day in one room of a given apartment cannot be in both model selection (training data) and the model evaluation (testing data) sets.

Each inner loop performs a grid search on a range of hyperparameters (GridSearchCV [79]): It trains 10 models on the respective training splits and tests them on the respective testing splits. There are numerous hyperparameters that can be included in such an optimization framework. However, a refined set of hyperparameters was selected based on recommendations for binary classification problems with XGBoost models [40]: *Learning rate* (to prevent overfitting), *max depth* (depth of trees), *number of estimators* (number of decision trees to be boosted), *gamma* (minimum loss reduction required to make a further partition on a leaf node of the tree), *subsample* (subsample ratio of the training instances), *colsample bytree* (subsample ratio of columns when constructing each tree) and *scale_pos_weight* (control of the balance between positive and negative weights).

In each fold of the outer loop, the best-performing model from the inner loop (highest MCC) is evaluated on the respective evaluation split. Once all outer loop folds are completed, the performance metrics are aggregated to assess the overall model performance, regardless of the model evaluation split.

There are around 260 000 parameter combinations for the nested cross-validation procedure. Lastly, a final model is trained on the entire curated dataset (with respect to the model type) with the optimum set of hyperparameters identified in a last stratified group k-fold cross-validation.

The nested cross-validation with hyperparameter optimization and training of the final models were performed on a Jupyter Notebook on the Southern Danish University Cloud (UCloud) [81]. The computer used at UCloud was an Intel Xeon Gold 6130 CPU with 64 cores and 384 GB of RAM. The final training, testing, analysis, and visualization were performed on a standard laptop computer (Intel Core i7-10510U CPU and 16 GB of RAM) using Python 3.11 on SPYDER 5.0.

5. Results and discussions

5.1. Selected features and feature importance

Fig. 12 shows the MCC of the different RF models (global model) with transforms of features as a function of the total number of features. One can observe that models without any CO₂-related features or including all four CO₂-related features perform significantly worse. The optimum number of CO₂-related features to include in the model seems to be two. Moreover, the optimum number of features to include in the model appears to be between 10 and 12. These observations hold for the room-specific models.

The results of the feature selection process for the six ODMs are presented in Fig. 13, which compares the relative importance of these features.¹ One can see that the *time of the day* is a feature of major importance, especially for the room-specific models. As expected, the one-hot encoded room type is crucial for the global model. Another expected result is that the current value of the indoor CO₂ concentration is a key feature in all models, as it is a very good indicator of human presence and activity in an indoor environment. On the other hand, the *current value* of the indoor operative temperature and relative humidity play a lesser role, appearing only in the room-specific bedroom model. Another noticeable observation is the high importance of the IEQ feature transforms accounting for the short-term and medium-term dynamics of the indoor environment, i.e., the *difference between the current value and the average of the past hour*, the *difference between the current value and the previously recorded value*, and the *mean average of the last hour*. The *difference between the current value and the average of the past hour* is very important, especially for the indoor CO₂ concentration, while the two other feature transforms are of lesser influence.

¹ Feature selection for the global model: 1) current CO₂ concentration, 2) difference between the current CO₂ concentration and the average of the past hour, 3) difference between the current operative temperature and the average of the past hour, 4) mean average temperature of the last hour, 5) difference between the current CO₂ concentration and the previously recorded value, 6) difference between the current operative temperature and the previously recorded value, 7) difference between the current relative humidity and the previously recorded value, 8) – 12) room type (hot-encoded), 13) – 14) time of the day (cos and sin cyclic encoding). Feature selection for the room-specific model (bedroom): 1) current value CO₂ concentration, 2) current operative temperature, 3) current relative humidity, 4) difference between the current CO₂ concentration and the average of the past hour, 5) difference between the current operative temperature and the average of the past hour, 6) difference between the current relative humidity and the average of the past hour, 7) – 8) time of the day (cos and sin cyclic encoding). Feature selection for the room-specific model (office): 1) current CO₂ concentration, 2) difference between the current CO₂ concentration and the average of the past hour, 3) difference between the current operative temperature and the average of the past hour, 4) difference between the current relative humidity and the average of the past hour, 4) – 5) time of the day (cos and sin cyclic encoding). Feature selection for the room-specific model (kitchen): 1) current CO₂ concentration, 2) difference between the current CO₂ concentration and the average of the past hour, 3) difference between the current operative temperature and the average of the past hour, 4) difference between the current relative humidity and the average of the past hour, 5) mean average CO₂ concentration of the last hour, 6) – 7) time of the day (cos and sin cyclic encoding). Feature selection for the room-specific model (living room): 1) current CO₂ concentration, 2) difference between the current CO₂ concentration and the average of the past hour, 3) difference between the current operative temperature and the average of the past hour, 4) – 5) time of the day (cos and sin cyclic encoding). Feature selection for the room-specific model (kitchen/living room): 1) difference between the current CO₂ concentration and the average of the past hour, 2) difference between the current operative temperature and the average of the past hour, 3) difference between the current CO₂ concentration and the previously recorded value, 4) difference between the current relative humidity and the previously recorded value, 5) and 6) time of the day (cos and sin cyclic encoding).

Fig. 12. MCC of the different RF models (global model) with permutations of features as a function of the total number of features, categorized by number of CO₂-related features (current value of indoor CO₂ concentration, difference between the current CO₂ concentration and the average of the past hour, difference between the current CO₂ concentration and the previously recorded value, and mean average CO₂ concentration of the latest four recordings). The solid lines indicate the average MCC of the models for a given number of features and CO₂-related features.

5.2. Global model performance

As explained above, to obtain a robust assessment of the ODMs, the nine performance metrics are aggregated over the different folds of the nested cross-validation process. These results for the global model when evaluated over all types of rooms are presented in Table 4. Overall, the global model performs very well: All nine metrics are in high-performing range, including the ones accounting for imbalanced dataset. Indeed, AUROC, *F1-score* and MCC all indicate that the model predicts occupancy and non-occupancy in a balanced way.

These results for the global model when evaluated over a specific room type are presented in Table 5. The ODM show varying performance across the different room types. The bedroom and kitchen/living room have relatively high scores, while the kitchen, living room, and office have lower scores. These good results for the bedroom and kitchen/living room could be explained by longer and more regular occupancy periods in those rooms with clearer correlated trends in the change of IEQ variables. In addition, these two room types have the lowest imbalance ratio in the ground truth data.

For the qualitative assessment, the time series of a typical day comparing the ground truth and predicted occupancy labels can be found in Figs. 14 and 15. The figures stem from the best performing model evaluation fold. As one can observe from these figures, the model's predictions are in good agreement with the occupancy ground truth. However, some minor misclassifications can be seen. One should note in Fig. 14 that it could appear that there is a delay between the ODM's predictions and the ground truth. This is purely coincidental and there is no systematic time offset in the model's predictions.

5.3. Room-specific model performance

The performance results of the room-specific models when evaluated over their respective room type are presented in Table 6. One can observe that these room-specific models perform the same for the

bedroom and kitchen/living room type when compared to the global model. However, the performance of the room-specific models is improved in the case of the kitchen, living room and office types. The latter results are expected as the room-specific models are tuned to fit the IEQ trends present in their respective datasets. The slight under-performance of both the global and room-specific models for the kitchen, office and living room might be caused by an imbalanced dataset with a lower number of points with occupancy for these respective rooms. Moreover, the kitchens and the living rooms might exchange a significant amount of air with adjacent rooms, which might disturb the correlations between IEQ trends and occupancy.

5.4. Model application and generalizability

In this subsection, the developed ODMs are applied to an unseen dataset (data originating from a different dwelling building case than the one used for model training (presented in section 3.2)). The ODMs' predictions are then compared to the occupancy ground truth of this application dataset in order to assess the generalizability of the ODMs.

Table 7 presents the global ODM performance for the two selected rooms in the application dataset. Similarly to the apartment block dataset, the model performs very well at predicting occupancy in the bedroom (comparable scores for all nine metrics). Conversely, the model's performance for the office declines significantly. The *recall* and *F1-score* are poor, suggesting that the model struggles to correctly identify true occupancy. Although the *precision* and *accuracy* are relatively high, the AUROC and MCC scores indicate that model performance is close to random guessing.

Table 8 presents the room-specific ODMs performance for the two selected rooms in the application dataset. The overall observations are very similar to the global model: Good predictions for the bedroom but very poor performance for the office room.

When looking specifically at the differences between the global and room-specific ODMs performance, one can see in Table 9. Overall, the

Fig. 13. Feature importance for each final model type.

Table 4

Average (Avg.) global model performance results from the nested cross-validation when applied to all room types, including standard deviation (Std. Dev.).

	Balanced accuracy	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Confusion matrix	F1-score	MCC	AUROC	Brier-score loss
Avg.	86 %	90 %	82 %	79 %	[1516 104] [122 407]	80 %	0.73	0.86	0.08
Std. Dev.	1.8 %	0.8 %	3.2 %	4.9 %	–	2.7 %	0.02	0.02	0.006

global model performs marginally better than the room-specific ones for most of the performance metrics in both room types. However, the difference is not significant: The global model only noticeably performs better in predicting the true positive occupancy in the office room (higher precision).

Figs. 16 and 17 present typical days in the application dataset (IEQ data, predicted occupancy and occupancy ground truth) for both the global and the room-specific model. As observed above, there are no significant differences between the global and the room-specific models for the bedroom: The predictions are in good agreement with the ground truth despite a few minor misclassified predictions. However, for the office room, both models present substantial and swift fluctuating predictions. This could be explained by the rapid changes in IEQ data, which may suggest large infiltrations from the bedroom into the office room, particularly during night-time hours. This could also be due to variations in the mechanical ventilation rate or quick door and window openings. More detailed contextual information about occupancy patterns, ventilation, air flow movement and behaviors (for example, door opening) could be incorporated into the model to enhance its predictive accuracy and generalizability.

The fluctuating predictions (false positives or false negatives) can

pose notable issues for HVAC control strategies if based on these models' output. On the one hand, in the case of false positives (no actual occupancy), energy use and costs might increase. On the other hand, false negatives (missing actual occupancy) can cause discomfort and dissatisfaction due to inadequate ventilation, heating, or cooling. If the potential for harm or dissatisfaction to occupants outweighs the energy saving from not running the system, then it is more important to minimize false negatives. Conversely, reducing false positives should be prioritized if the cost and environmental impact of wasted energy is a significant concern. Ultimately, an optimal balance should be aimed to minimize false predictions and ensure efficient, comfortable, and sustainable operations using data-driven occupant detection for control systems. Domain-knowledge-based pre and post data treatment could be a potential solution to eliminate rapid fluctuating occupancy predictions, e.g., rule-based exclusion of short absence within long occupancy periods.

6. Conclusions and suggestions for future investigations

The current study aimed at developing and assessing the performance of occupant detection models based on the XGBoost

Table 5
Average global model performance results from the nested cross-validation when applied to a specific room type, including standard deviation (Std. Dev.).

	Bedroom	Kitchen	Living room	Office	Kitchen/living room
Balanced accuracy	93 %	65 %	75 %	63 %	86 %
Std. Dev.	1.9 %	4 %	8.8 %	9 %	2.5 %
Accuracy	93 %	83 %	86 %	95 %	87 %
Std. Dev.	1.5 %	5.7 %	3.3 %	2.4 %	2.5 %
Precision	90 %	43 %	70 %	52 %	87 %
Std. Dev.	2.9 %	11 %	9.8 %	25 %	3.7 %
Recall	91 %	39 %	57 %	27 %	92 %
Std. Dev.	4.5 %	10 %	19 %	18 %	5.2 %
Confusion matrix	[493 28] [24 253]	[290 20] [35 22]	[317 21] [37 48]	[323 5] [13 5]	[92 22] [13 142]
F1-score	91 %	41 %	63 %	36 %	89 %
Std. Dev.	1.8 %	9 %	17 %	21 %	2.7 %
MCC	0.86	0.31	0.55	0.35	0.73
Std. Dev.	0.03	0.08	0.15	0.21	0.05
AUROC	0.93	0.65	0.75	0.63	0.86
Std. Dev.	0.02	0.04	0.9	0.09	0.02
Brier-score loss	0.05	0.12	0.10	0.04	0.10
Std. Dev.	0.01	0.030	0.02	0.02	0.02

methodology. To that matter, a detailed measurement campaign was conducted in a multi-story apartment block in Denmark to collect IEQ data and occupancy ground truth in different flats and room types. Although covering only seven days of monitoring, this dataset is currently the largest of its kind and has been made available for open access. This dataset was then used to perform feature selection and importance analysis for two types of modeling approaches: A global

model, trained on data from all room types, and room-based models, trained on sub-datasets that are specific to their respective room types. Based on the systematic testing of numerous feature combinations, it was found that the time of the day and the indoor CO₂ concentration were crucial features for the good performance of IEQ-based occupancy detection models. Moreover, feature transforms related to short-term IEQ dynamics, e.g., the change of CO₂ concentration within the last hour, have also been found to be of great importance.

When evaluated on the building case dataset, the models generally perform very well, especially for bedrooms and kitchens/living rooms, without significant differences between the global and room-specific models. However, lower performance is observed for kitchen, office and living room types. When tested on a dataset originating from a different building case (unseen data from a single-family house) both model types demonstrated robustness and promising results for the bedroom, but performed less satisfactorily for the office room, which underlines limitations in terms of generalizability. The discrepancy in performance may be attributed to large differences in occupancy and ventilation patterns, and significant air infiltration from adjacent rooms. It could be valuable to conduct additional testing in various room types and settings to understand the model’s capabilities and limitations better.

When building a machine learning model for predicting a specific outcome based on IEQ data, a key challenge emerges from the seasonal variation in occupant behavior (window opening and heating/cooling system operation) and presence, especially in Nordic countries with typically three distinct seasons. The present occupancy models are specifically trained for winter conditions in residential buildings, which might result in very poor predictive performance for other seasons or other building types.

Future work regarding the refinement of the models could focus on handling the fluctuating occupancy predictions better. To that end, different model architectures could be more appropriate, such as sequence-to-sequence transformer/encoder-decoder deep neural networks. Furthermore, extending the ground truth period and incorporating scenarios such as vacations or weekends could enhance the model’s robustness. Lastly, the model could be trained and tested across a broader range of building types, ventilation settings, and occupancy patterns to reinforce its robustness and generalizability.

Finally, the implementation of occupancy detection-based applications in building management systems is sparse. Future research should

Fig. 14. Comparison between occupancy ground truth and model’s prediction for two typical days in a bedroom (room 13).

Fig. 15. Comparison between occupancy ground truth and model's prediction for two typical days in a kitchen/living room (room 2).

Table 6

Average room-specific models performance results from the nested cross-validation, including standard deviation (Std. Dev.).

	Bedroom	Kitchen	Living room	Office	Kitchen/ living room
Balanced accuracy	94 %	72 %	82 %	75 %	86 %
Std. Dev.	1.6 %	4.3 %	5.2 %	1 %	2.9 %
Accuracy	94 %	77 %	86 %	94 %	87 %
Std. Dev.	1.2 %	4.3 %	2.8 %	3.4 %	3.3 %
Precision	93 %	42 %	66 %	35 %	87 %
Std. Dev.	3 %	10 %	6 %	10 %	4.8 %
Recall	91 %	64 %	73 %	55 %	90 %
Std. Dev.	3.6 %	10 %	12 %	17 %	4.3 %
Confusion matrix	[425 15] [22 211]	[301 81] [31 58]	[344 37] [30 72]	[441 20] [10 10]	[100 22] [16 151]
F1-score	92 %	50 %	68 %	41 %	88 %
Std. Dev.	1.6 %	8 %	5.3 %	8.6 %	3.7 %
MCC	0.88	0.38	0.61	0.40	0.73
Std. Dev.	0.024	0.084	0.063	0.10	0.061
AUROC	0.94	0.72	0.82	0.75	0.86
Std. Dev.	0.015	0.043	0.05	0.09	0.029
Briar-score loss	0.04	0.16	0.12	0.06	0.1
Std. Dev.	0.011	0.03	0.034	0.04	0.023
Computational time	2 h	2 h	1.6 h	2 h	1.5 h

also investigate the practical implementation of occupant-centric controls and occupant-aware building performance assessments (e.g., KPIs) leveraging occupancy detection models.

Table 7

Global model performance on the application dataset for the bedroom and office [32].

	Bedroom	Office
Balanced accuracy	93 %	52 %
Accuracy	93 %	87 %
Precision	95 %	73 %
Recall	88 %	5 %
Confusion matrix	[688 23] [58 435]	[1038 3] [155 8]
F1-score	92 %	10 %
MCC	0.86	0.16
AUROC	0.93	0.52
Briar-score loss	0.07	0.13

Table 8

Room-specific model performance on the application dataset for the bedroom and office.

	Bedroom	Office
Balanced accuracy	91 %	52 %
Accuracy	92 %	84 %
Precision	97 %	24 %
Recall	84 %	10 %
Confusion matrix	[700 11] [80 413]	[994 47] [148 15]
F1-score	90 %	13 %
MCC	0.85	0.07
AUROC	0.91	0.52
Briar-score loss	0.08	0.16

Funding

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and several partners through the research project "Self-Assessment Towards Optimization of Building Energy" (SATO, <https://www.sato-project.eu/>), grant agreement No. 957128.

Data statement

The collected and curated dataset containing occupancy ground

Table 9
Comparison of the models' performance: Global model minus room-specific model.

	Bedroom	Office
Balanced accuracy	2 %	0 %
Accuracy	1 %	3 %
Precision	-2 %	49 %
Recall	4 %	-5 %
Confusion matrix	[-12 12] [-22 22]	[44-44] [7-7]
F1-score	2 %	-3 %
MCC	0.01	0.09
AUROC	0.02	0
Briar-score loss	-0.01	-0.03

truth and IEQ measurements for the multi-story residential building can be downloaded from a dedicated Zenodo repository [82]. The code for occupant detection modeling, figures and analyses, and supplementary

material can be found at the in a dedicated GitHub repository [48].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kamilla Heimar Andersen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hicham Johra:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Markus Schaffer:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Anna Marszal-Pomianowska:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Henrik N. Knudsen:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Data curation. **Per Kvolts Heiselberg:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **William O'Brien:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation,

Fig. 16. The top figure shows the IEQ data, the middle figure shows the global model predicted occupancy and ground truth, and the bottom figure shows the room-specific model predicted occupancy and ground truth over a representative period for the bedroom.

Fig. 17. The top figure shows the IEQ data, the middle figure shows the global model predicted occupancy and ground truth, and the bottom figure shows the room-specific model predicted occupancy and ground truth over a representative period for the office.

Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

A thank you to the participants from Aalborg University in the SmartVENT project for <https://www.smartvent.aau.dk/> the data access to the single-family house, allowing to test the developed models' generalizability.

A huge gratitude towards the occupants for spending their time filling out the logbook.

Part of the computation done for this project was performed on the

UCloud interactive HPC system, which is managed by the eScience Center at the University of Southern Denmark <https://cloud.sdu.dk/app/dashboard>.

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